

Manuscript Number: NBD-18-496

Title: Does seipin play a role in oxidative stress protection and peroxisome biogenesis? New insights from human brain autopsies.

Article Type: Research paper

Keywords: BSCL2; Seipin; Human brain; Oxidative stress; Peroxisomes; SH-SY5Y; Gene expression; PELD; Neurodegeneration; Lipodystrophy

Corresponding Author: Professor David Araujo-Vilar,

Corresponding Author's Institution: Universidade de Santiago de Compostela

First Author: Sofia Sánchez-Iglesias, PhD

Order of Authors: Sofia Sánchez-Iglesias, PhD; Alberto Fernández-Liste, MD; Cristina Guillín-Amarelle, MD PhD; Alberto Rábano, MD PhD; Leticia Rodríguez-Cañete, MD; Antía Fernández-Pombo, MD; Ana Senra; David Araujo-Vilar

Abstract: Seipin is among the 74% of human proteins expressed in the brain, and its gene BSCL2 one of the 7,319 genes expressed in all tissues, predominantly in brain and testes. Seipin function is not yet completely understood, therefore the aim of this study was to evaluate the expression of BSCL2 transcripts in the central nervous system (CNS) of humans and investigate the effect of their overexpression on a neuron model and their relationship with oxidative stress protection, as well as shed light on the pathogenic mechanisms of Celia's Encephalopathy. We analyzed the expression of BSCL2 transcripts using real-time RT-PCR in samples across the brain regions of subjects who underwent necropsy and from a case with Celia's Encephalopathy. The transcript encoding the long seipin isoform (BSCL2-203, 462 aa) is expressed primarily in the brain and its expression is inversely correlated with age in the temporal lobe, amygdala, and hypothalamus. Strong positive correlations were found between BSCL2 expression and some genes encoding protective enzymes against oxidative stress including SOD1 and SOD2, as well as PPARG in the amygdala. These results were experimentally corroborated by overexpressing BSCL2 transcripts in SH-SY5Y cells with lentiviral transduction and assessing their effects on neuron differentiated cells. Confocal microscopy studies showed that both seipin and PEX16 are closely expressed in the hypothalami of healthy human brains, and PEX16 was absent in the same region of the PELD case. We hypothesize that seipin has specific CNS functions and may play a role in peroxisome biogenesis.

Suggested Reviewers: Justin Rochford PhD
Reader, The University of Aberdeen
j.rochford@abdn.ac.uk
Expert in seipin function

Daisuke Ito M.D. Ph.D.
Assistant Professor, Department of Neurology, Keio University

d-ito@jk9.so-net.ne.jp
Expert in seipinopathies

Qi Wan MD
Department of Neurology, Nanjing Medical University
qi_wan@126.com
Expert in seipin function in brain.

Opposed Reviewers:

May 25th, 2018

Prof. Timothy Greenamyre
Editor-in-Chief
Neurobiology of Disease

Dear Prof. Greenamyre,

On behalf of my coauthors, please find attached the manuscript entitled "Does seipin play a role in oxidative stress protection and peroxisome biogenesis? New insights from human brain autopsies" We hope that you find this manuscript to be of interest to the readership of *Neurobiology of Disease*.

Seipin is an endoplasmic reticulum resident protein encoded by BSCL2 gene. Although its main function has been related with lipid droplets biogenesis, and homozygous variants in BSCL2 are responsible of congenital generalized lipodystrophy (CGL), the fact is that this gene is highly expressed in brain, more than in adipose tissue. On the other hand, our group discovered five years ago a CGL variant (PELD), coursing with a severe neurodegenerative disorder, resulting fatal in children. In order to unveil a putative seipin brain function, we have explored the relative expression of the different BSCL2 transcripts in the brain and extraneural tissues coming from 13 subjects who undergone a forensic autopsy. We have also included molecular and histological information coming from a case deceased as a consequence of PELD. We found a differential expression of the three main BSCL2 transcripts in brain and extraneural tissues of the studied subjects, being that encoding the largest seipin much more expressed in brain. Also interesting was the fact that the expression of this transcript was progressively reduced with aging. We found also that BSCL2 expression strongly correlated with genes encoding proteins involved in oxidative stress protection and peroxisome biogenesis. These findings were confirmed using a cellular neuronal model overexpressing *BSCL2*. Finally, using confocal microscopy we found that seipin and PEX16 (a membrane peroxisomal protein), although not co-localize, they appears to be closely intertwined, and perhaps more interesting, no PEX16 was detected in seipin deficient PELD case. Taking together these results are highly suggestive that seipin is playing an important role in protection against oxidative stress in human brain, probably through a not yet discovered mechanism on peroxisome biogenesis.

This contribution represents original work and has not been previously published or simultaneously submitted for publication elsewhere.

Thank you for your consideration of this manuscript.

Kind Regards,

David Araújo-Villar, MD, PhD
UETeM, Lab 3
Biomedical Research Institute (CIMUS)
Rua Barcelona 3
15707 Santiago de Compostela, Spain
E-mail: david.araujo@usc.es

Highlights

- *BSCL2* expression in human brains decreases with age
- *BSCL2* expression correlates with oxidative stress protection and peroxisome biogenesis genes
- Seipin and PEX16 are closely expressed in some brain areas
- PEX16 is not present in the brain of a patient with PELD

Does seipin play a role in oxidative stress protection and peroxisome biogenesis? New insights from human brain autopsies.

Short title: Seipin and the human brain

Sofia Sánchez-Iglesias^a, Alberto Fernández-Liste^b, Cristina Guillín-Amarelle^a, Alberto Rábano^c, Leticia Rodríguez-Cañete^a, Blanca González-Méndez^a, Antía Fernández-Pombo^a, Ana^d, David Araújo-Vilar^{a,*}

Author Affiliation:

a) Thyroid and Metabolic Diseases Unit (U.E.T.eM.), Department of Psychiatry, Radiology, Public Health, Nursing and Medicine (Medicine Area), Center for Research in Molecular Medicine and Chronic Diseases (CIMUS)-IDIS, University of Santiago de Compostela, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain.

b) Instituto de Medicina Legal de Galicia (IMELGA), 15707 Santiago de Compostela, A Coruña, Spain.

c) Neuropathology Department and Tissue Bank, Fundación CIEN, 28031 Madrid, Spain

d) Department of Physiology, Center for Research in Molecular Medicine and Chronic Diseases (CIMUS)-IDIS, University of Santiago de Compostela, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain.

*Corresponding author

Address for correspondence:

David Araújo-Vilar, MD PhD

U.E.T.eM., Department of Psychiatry, Radiology, Public Health, Nursing and Medicine -IDIS CIMUS, Avda. de Barcelona 3

University of Santiago de Compostela

15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain.

Phone: +34 881815426 Fax: +34 981559937

E-mail: david.araujo@usc.es

Abstract

Seipin is among the 74% of human proteins expressed in the brain, and its gene *BSCL2* one of the 7,319 genes expressed in all tissues, predominantly in brain and testes. Seipin function is not yet completely understood, therefore the aim of this study was to evaluate the expression of *BSCL2* transcripts in the central nervous system (CNS) of humans and investigate the effect of their overexpression on a neuron model and their relationship with oxidative stress protection, as well as shed light on the pathogenic mechanisms of Celia's Encephalopathy. We analyzed the expression of *BSCL2* transcripts using real-time RT-PCR in samples across the brain regions of subjects who underwent necropsy and from a case with Celia's Encephalopathy. The transcript encoding the long seipin isoform (*BSCL2*-203, 462 aa) is expressed primarily in the brain and its expression is inversely correlated with age in the temporal lobe, amygdala, and hypothalamus. Strong positive correlations were found between *BSCL2* expression and some genes encoding protective enzymes against oxidative stress including *SOD1* and *SOD2*, as well as *PPARG* in the amygdala. These results were experimentally corroborated by overexpressing *BSCL2* transcripts in SH-SY5Y cells with lentiviral transduction and assessing their effects on neuron differentiated cells. Confocal microscopy studies showed that both seipin and PEX16 are closely expressed in the hypothalami of healthy human brains, and PEX16 was absent in the same region of the PELD case. We hypothesize that seipin has specific CNS functions and may play a role in peroxisome biogenesis.

Keywords: *BSCL2*; Seipin; Human brain; Oxidative stress; Peroxisomes; SH-SY5Y; Gene expression; PELD; Neurodegeneration; Lipodystrophy.

Words count: Abstract: 246; Text: 4405; 30220 characters incl. space

1. Introduction

The *BSCL2* gene encodes seipin, a resident endoplasmic reticulum (ER) protein with two transmembrane domains, a luminal loop, and two amino and carboxy-terminal tails in the cytoplasm.

The *BSCL2* gene principally encodes three seipin isoforms under natural conditions, 462 (*BSCL2*-203, ENST00000360796.9; CCDS44627), 398 (*BSCL2*-205/207/210, ENST00000403550.5; ENST00000407022.7; ENST00000421906.5; CCDS8031), and 287 (*BSCL2*-201, ENST00000278893.11; CCDS55769) amino acids long, respectively. *BSCL2*-210/207/205 was the first transcript to be described (Magre et al., 2001), and *BSCL2*-203 is the same as *BSCL2*-210/207/205 except for an N-terminal extension of 64 amino acids encoded by exon 1 and part of exon 2. The protein translated from the short transcript is different from the other transcripts, as exon 7 is skipped in *BSCL2*-201 and the reading frame is different from exon 6 to exon 10 (Guillen-Navarro et al., 2013).

In humans, seipin forms 12 unit homoligomers that form a toroid (Sim et al., 2013; Sim et al., 2014). *BSCL2* variants can cause different diseases, such as generalized congenital lipodystrophy type 2 (MIM: # 269700), seipinopathies of first and/or second motor neurons (MIM: # 600794, MIM: # 270685) (Ito and Suzuki, 2009), or Progressive Encephalopathy with or without lipodystrophy, also called Celia's Encephalopathy (PELD, MIM: # 615924) (Guillen-Navarro et al., 2013).

PELD is an infantile neurodegenerative disease with a fatal prognosis before 9 years previously described by our group (Guillen-Navarro et al., 2013). Neurological regression of Celia's Encephalopathy begins at age 3-4, with early signs of severe

myoclonic epilepsy, spastic tetraparesis, and severe encephalopathy leading to death before age 9. This disease is extraordinarily rare, and is a consequence of the *BSCL2* gene c.985C>T variant in homozygosis or compound heterozygosis (Alaei et al., 2016; Guillen-Navarro et al., 2013). This variant gives rise to a branch site in exon 7 of the *BSCL2* gene, producing the intronization of that exon leading to an aberrant seipin with a different amino acid sequence than wild-type (*BSCL2*-203) from exon 6 (Guillen-Navarro et al., 2013). The formation of large aberrant seipin macroaggregates leading to ER stress and nuclear accumulation of this abnormal protein are the pathogenetic mechanisms ultimately responsible for Celia's Encephalopathy (Ruiz-Riquelme et al., 2015).

Seipin is a highly evolutionarily conserved protein functioning primarily to modulate the formation of lipid droplets and identified in yeast, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Caenorhabditis elegans*, zebrafish, fruit fly, and mammals (Cartwright and Goodman, 2012; Salo et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2016). While this gene is mainly expressed in the central nervous system (CNS), pituitary gland, and testis in humans (Guillen-Navarro et al., 2013; Magre et al., 2001), little is known about the function of seipin in the CNS. Recent studies in seipin KO mice have shown a particular action for this protein in the CNS that appears to be mediated by peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPARG) and that influences synaptic transmission primarily through α -amino-3-hydroxy-5-methyl-4-isoxazolepropionic acid receptors, and also promotes neuronal differentiation and modulates the behavior and motor skills of these animals (Ebihara et al., 2015; Li et al., 2015; Zhou et al., 2016). Here we evaluate the expression of the various *BSCL2* transcripts across human brain regions and extraneural tissues and investigate the putative functions of seipin in the CNS.

2. Subjects, Materials and Methods

This study was approved by the Ethics Review panel of Xunta de Galicia (Spain) and performed in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the Helsinki Declaration.

2.1. Tissue samples

Thirteen post-mortem donors were selected, 7 men and 6 women (aged 21 to 86 years), primarily deceased by suicide, traffic accident, or natural causes (see Table S4, Supplementary Material) in accordance with the current Spanish legislation, and tissue samples were obtained during autopsy conducted within 24 hours of death. Brains were removed and sliced coronally into 12 sections. The frontal cortices in the third slice, parietal and temporal cortices with hippocampi in the seventh slice, occipital lobes in the eleventh, insular cortices, amygdalae, thalami, heads of caudate and putamen nuclei, and cerebellum samples were accurately dissected and collected separately from both cerebral and cerebellar hemispheres, along with the right and left sides of the hypothalamus, mesencephalon, protuberance, and medulla oblongata, as well as the dorsal and ventral spinal cord, anterior pituitary, vagus and trigeminal nerves, skeletal muscles (rectus abdominis and gastrocnemius), adipose tissue from Bichat's fat pad, abdominal subcutaneous tissue, visceral areas and lower limbs, renal cortex and medulla, and liver and gonad samples. These tissues were immediately submerged in liquid nitrogen after removal and subsequently stored at -80 °C until RNA preparation. These dissections yielded a total of 44 tissues for real-time RT-PCR analysis.

2.2. RNA extraction and retrotranscription

Total RNA was isolated with the ReliaPrep™ RNA Tissue Miniprep System (Promega, Madrid, Spain) (see Supplementary Material for detailed protocol). The RNA was reverse transcribed using M-MLV reverse transcriptase (Invitrogen), as previously described (Victoria et al., 2010).

2.3. Real-time RT-PCR

Specific primers and probes designed by the Universal ProbeLibrary (Roche Diagnostics, Sant Cugat del Valles, Spain) were used in a Light Cycler 2.0 (Roche Diagnostics) to determine the specific expression of the following genes: *CAT*, *Nestin*, *PEX1*, *PPARG*, *RBFOX3/NeuN*, *SOD1*, *SOD2* (Table S5, Supplementary Material), and three distinct *BSCL2* transcripts (Figure S3, Supplementary Material). Real-time RT-PCR conditions are available upon request. Results were normalized to the *18S* and *RNA polymerase II* genes using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001).

2.4. Cell culture

The SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cell line was kindly provided by Dr. Jesús Rodríguez-Requena (Santiago de Compostela, Spain). Undifferentiated cells were maintained in a 1:1 mixture of Ham's F12 (cat. N4888, Sigma-Aldrich) and Minimum Essential Eagle's Medium (cat. M2279, Sigma-Aldrich) supplemented with 15% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (cat. 10270-106, Gibco), 1% GlutaMax-I™ (cat. 35050-061, Gibco), 100 units/ml penicillin, 100 µg/ml streptomycin (cat. 15140-122, Gibco), and 1% MEM non-essential amino acids solution (NEAA, cat. 11140050, Gibco). Cells were grown in the presence of 5% CO₂ in a humidified incubator at 37 °C. The cell medium was replaced every 3 days, and the cells were sub-cultured once 90% confluence was reached. The cells were used at early passages (below P17) in all experiments.

2.5. Plasmids

A plasmid containing wild type human seipin fused to a myc tag (6x myc-wt seipin pCS2+MT) was generously provided by D. Ito (Keio University, Japan), and the myc fused seipin expression plasmid was described previously (Guillen-Navarro et al., 2013). The wild type lentiviral plasmid was generated as follows: wt seipin cDNA was amplified by PCR using specific primers (forward: 5'-TAAGCAGGTACCTCTTTTTGCAGGATCCCATCGA-3'; reverse: 5'-TAAGCATCTAGAGCCTTGAATTCGCCCTTGAC-3'), then digested with the fast-digest restriction enzymes KpnI and XbaI (cat. FD0524 and FD0684, ThermoFisher Scientific), and purified and inserted into pLenti-CMV-GFP-2A-Puro-Blank (cat. LV073, Applied Biological Materials Inc.) vector. This GFP bicistronic lentiviral plasmid is a replication-incompetent third generation vector, and is depicted in Figure S4 (Supplementary Material). Full sequences were confirmed by sequencing.

2.6. Lentiviral transduction

Cells were seeded into 6-well plates (cat. 3516, Corning, Costar) at a density of 5.000 cells per cm². The medium was removed twenty-four hours after seeding and the cells were washed with phosphate buffered saline (PBS). Viral particles (wild-type seipin), and the empty vector as a control, all with functional titers > 10⁹ transducing units/ml) produced by Cyagen Biosciences (Guangzhou, China) were added at a multiplicity of infection (MOI) of 200 viral particles/cell to a serum-free medium in the presence of Lentiblast A/B (1:100/1:1000, Oz Biosciences, Marseille, France). Serum was added 4

hours after initial infection (final infection volume 1 ml), the medium was removed twenty-four hours after infection, and the cells were washed with phosphate buffered saline (PBS). Cells were then cultured with typical SH-SY5Y medium and puromycin dihydrochloride (2 µg/ml final concentration, cat. P8833, Sigma-Aldrich) was subsequently added to the cell culture medium every 2–3 days until resistant stable cells were formed. Cells were then routinely grown as described above.

2.7. Differentiation

Stably transfected cells were seeded into 6-well plates at density of 10.000 cells per cm² and allowed to adhere for 2 days. Pre-differentiation was then started in DMEM high glucose (D5796, Sigma-Aldrich) supplemented with 3% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum, 100 units/ml penicillin, and 100 µg/ml streptomycin with 10 µM retinoic acid (cat. R2625, Sigma-Aldrich), freshly prepared in DMSO and kept in the dark. Undifferentiated cells were cultured in identical medium without retinoic acid. The second phase of differentiation was initiated after 3 days in these conditions (day 4) with Neurobasal medium (cat. 21103-049, Gibco), 50 ng/ml BDNF (cat. 450-02, Peprotech), 1 mM dibutyryl-cAMP (cat. sc-201567A, Santa Cruz), 20 mM KCl (cat. 131494, Panreac), 10 µM retinoic acid, 1% B27 (cat. 17504-044, Gibco), 1% Glutamax 100x, 1% N-2 supplement (cat. 17502-048, Gibco), 100 units/ml penicillin, and 100 µg/ml streptomycin. Undifferentiated cells were maintained in high glucose DMEM, supplemented with 1% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum, 100 units/ml penicillin, and 100 µg/ml streptomycin. The culture medium was changed every 2 days and supplemented with fresh additives. Differences in cell morphology between proliferative and differentiated cells were evaluated under phase contrast light

microscopy with an Olympus IX51 microscope (Olympus Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) and photographed with an Olympus DP72 digital camera using the cellSens software (Olympus Corporation). Cells were harvested on day 8.

2.8. Immunostaining

The hypothalamus of the homozygous index case c.985C>T and of two control cases (male and female, 59 and 75 years at death, respectively) were fixed previously with 10% neutral buffered formalin (Bio-Optica, cat. 05-K01022) for 24 hours at room temperature and embedded in paraffin. After deparaffinization and rehydration, slides were pre-treated with PT-link (Dako, California, USA) for 20 minutes at 95 °C in Tris/EDTA buffer, pH 9. Slides were then washed four times with PBS and incubated with 1:250 anti PEX16 antibody (Santa Cruz Biotechnology) and 1:125 anti-seipin antibody HPA042394 (Sigma-Aldrich, The Human Protein Atlas) overnight at 4 °C. The next day, the slides were washed four times with PBS and incubated with Alexa Fluor 555 (Thermo-Fisher Scientific, cat. A31572) conjugated anti-mouse secondary antibody, and Alexa Fluor 488 (Thermo-Fisher Scientific, cat. A21202) conjugated anti-rabbit secondary antibody for 1 h in darkness, washed with double-distilled water. Slides were then treated to quench autofluorescence background with 0.1% Sudan Black B (Sigma, cat. 199664) in 70% ethanol for less than 5 minutes at room temperature and washed three times, for 5 minutes each with double-distilled water. Finally, they were mounted in aqueous medium containing 1:1000 DAPI (Sigma-Aldrich, cat. D9542).

2.9. Confocal fluorescence microscopy

Immunofluorescence staining was assessed with a Leica TCS SP2 confocal microscope using a HCX PL APO 63x/1.3 glycerol-immersion objective and Leica Confocal Software (Leica Microsystems Heidelberg GmbH, Mannheim, Germany). Images were obtained by a sequential scan method and three different laser lines to avoid simultaneous excitation and possible overlap. Confocal acquisition of the fluorescence labels was performed as follows: DAPI, color-coded in blue (Blue-Diode, excited at 405 nm and recorded on 425-470 nm), Alexa Fluor 488 nm, color-coded in green (Argon laser, excited at 488 nm and recorded at 500-555 nm), and Alexa Fluor 555 nm, color-coded in red (DPS diode, excited at 561 nm and recorded at 581-675 nm). Two random visual fields were analyzed for each group.

2.10. Statistical analysis

Real-time PCR analyses were done by duplicates, and statistical significance was determined using a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test followed by a Mann-Whitney U post-hoc with Bonferroni correction. Correlations were tested using the Spearman R correlation coefficient and partial correlations were utilized to correlate two variables while adjusting for other one. Data are presented as mean \pm SD with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS for Mac (release 22.0; SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Patterns of *BSCL2* expression in human tissues

We evaluated the relative expression of seipin transcripts in the CNS, the peripheral nervous system (PNS), and extraneural tissues (ET) in 13 subjects (Figure 1A, detailed with significance in Table S1, Supplementary Material). The total expression of *BSCL2*

was 6.9 times higher in the CNS than in any of the other tissues ($p < 0.001$): 86.3% in CNS, 1.3% in PNS, and 12.4% in ET (Figure 1B), and the pituitary and the gonads had the highest total *BSCL2* expression of the non-neural tissues (5.25% and 2.61%, respectively). The predominant transcript is *BSCL2-203* (x6.8), which encodes the long isoform and represents 86.6% of total *BSCL2* transcript expression (Figure 1B). *BSCL2-203* was expressed most in the CNS (78.9% of total *BSCL2* expression, and 91.2% of *BSCL2-203* expression) (Figure 1B-C) and was higher in the caudate nuclei and in the protuberance (9.2% and 9% of *BSCL2-203* expression, respectively). *BSCL2-203* expression in the PNS and ET was 0.9% and 7.9%, respectively (Figure 1C). *BSCL2-205/207/210* expression represented only 12.7% of total *BSCL2* expression (Figure 1B) and was expressed the most in ET and the PNS (42.6% and 4.1% of *BSCL2-205/207/210* expression, respectively) (Figure 1C). *BSCL2-205/207/210* expression was increased 3.9x and 2x respectively in adipose and muscle tissues, compared to *BSCL2-203*, and *BSCL2-201* expression was low in all tissues (0.7% of total *BSCL2* expression, Figure 1B). Within the CNS, the short transcript was primarily expressed in the caudate nucleus, the cerebellum, and the protuberance. Expression levels of *BSCL2* transcripts across the primary brain divisions are summarized in Figure 1C.

A comparison of *BSCL2* expression between men and women (Table S2, Supplementary Material) shows that the three transcripts are expressed more highly in the testicles than in the ovaries (*BSCL2-203*: +54%, $p = 0.003$; *BSCL2-205/207/210*: +2559%, $p = 0.0001$; *BSCL2-201*: +345%, $p = 0.0001$), and *BSCL2-203* and *BSCL2-205/207/210* are more expressed in the ventral spinal cord in men than in women (+164%, $p = 0.008$; and +71%, $p = 0.02$, respectively). *BSCL2-203* expression is significantly higher in the

temporal lobe in men than in women (Right: +57%, $p=0.046$; Left: +46%, $p=0.04$), the visceral fat (-33%, $p=0.023$), and the vagus nerve (+43%, $p=0.017$) (Table S2A, Supplementary Material). *BSCL2*-205/207/210 expression in the left temporal lobe (+408%, $p=0.01$), left insula (+194%, $p=0.01$), left hypothalamus (+155%, $p=0.01$), subcutaneous abdominal fat (+69%, $p=0.003$), and vagus and trigeminal nerves (+83%, $p=0.001$; and +108%, $p=0.018$, respectively) are significantly higher in men than in women, while expression in men is lower in the rectus abdominis muscle and the left frontal lobe (-42%, $p=0.015$; -63%, $p=0.02$, respectively) (Table S2B, Supplementary Material) compared to women. Finally, *BSCL2*-201 expression in the pituitary and the right cerebellum are significantly lower in men than in women (-40%, $p=0.003$, and -67%, $p=0.015$, respectively) (Table S2C, Supplementary Material).

3.2. Influence of age on *BSCL2* expression

A comparison of *BSCL2* expression between young and aged individuals (median age 61 years, Table S3, Supplementary Material) shows that *BSCL2* transcripts are generally expressed more highly in younger subjects in both encephalic and non-encephalic tissues. This observation is strongest for *BSCL2*-203 (Table S3A, Supplementary Material), weaker for *BSCL2*-201 (Table S3C, Supplementary Material), and weakest for *BSCL2*-205/207/210 (Table S3B, Supplementary Material). An analysis of the correlations between *BSCL2*-203 transcript and age using Spearman's correlation coefficient revealed significant negative correlations in the left temporal lobe ($r= -0.83$, $p<0.001$), left hypothalamus ($r= -0.67$, $p<0.05$), and left amygdala ($r= -0.62$, $p<0.05$) (Figure 2).

3.3. Putative role for seipin on oxidative stress protection and peroxisome biogenesis in the CNS

3.3.1. qPCR studies in human brains

Based on the previous correlation results, the well-know role for oxidative stress in aging (López-Otín et al., 2013), and our own preadipocyte proteomic results from a Celia's Encephalopathy case (Ruiz-Riquelme et al . 2015) indicating that mitochondrial superoxide dismutase (*SOD2*) and glutathione peroxidase were distinctively modulated, we decided to quantify the expression of key genes related to oxidative stress protection by qPCR in the left temporal lobe, left amygdala and left hypothalamus: *PPARG*, cytoplasmic superoxide dismutase (*SOD1*), mitochondrial superoxide dismutase (*SOD2*), catalase (*CAT*) and peroxisomal biogenesis factor 1 (*PEX1*). Spearman's partial correlation coefficients were calculated and strong positive correlations were found between *BSCL2-203* and *SOD1* and *SOD2*: *BSCL2-203/SOD1*, $r= 0.9$, $p<0.001$ and *BSCL2-203/SOD2*, $r= 0.6$, $p=0.048$, in left amygdala; *BSCL2-203/SOD2*, $r= 0.9$, $p<0.001$, in left temporal lobe. We found an important positive correlation between *PPARG* and *BSCL2-203* in the amygdala and hypothalamus ($r= 0.8$, $p=0.03$, in left amygdala; $r= 0.8$, $p<0.002$, in left hypothalamus). Considering that *PPARG* plays an important role in the activation of peroxisome proliferation, we measured the expression of *PEX1* in the left amygdala, *PEX1* encodes peroxisome biogenesis factor 1, an ATPase anchored to the peroxisomal membrane, and plays a role in protein import into peroxisomes and peroxisome biogenesis, in addition to the catalase enzyme (*CAT*) also present in peroxisomes. *BSCL2* did not correlate with *CAT* or *PEX1* when applying partial correlation coefficients.

3.3.2. In vitro studies

Since the observed correlations do not imply causality, we differentiate SH-SY5Y cells stably transfected with *BSCL2* into a neuronal model cell line in order to measure the expression of genes significantly correlated with *BSCL2* in human brains. Morphological changes were observed after 3-5 days (Figure 3), and many SH-SY5Y cells stopped proliferating and expanded an extensive network of long neurites. At the end of differentiation (day 7), cells were evenly distributed and developed a more rounded shape, forming clumps of cell bodies linked by long processes similar to axons (Figure 3C).

Neuronal differentiation was assessed by quantifying the mRNA expression levels of neurogenesis-related genes specific for neural progenitors (*Nestin*) and mature neurons (*NeuN/RBFOX3*), playing an essential role in the differentiation and maturation of neural progenitor cells (Kim et al., 2009; Kim et al., 2013). The results showed that the mRNA expression of both neuronal markers was detected in non-differentiated cells and significantly increased after 7 days of differentiation, pointing toward a more neuronal phenotype. *Nestin* and *NeuN/RBFOX3* increased approximately 4-to 5-fold and 2-to 10-fold, respectively (Figure S1A-B). The expression of the *BSCL2*-203 transcript was much higher in *BSCL2*-cells than in control cells (+3024%) (Figure 4A). While there was no significant difference for *PEXI*, significantly higher relative expression was seen for *PPARG* (+93,5%) and the antioxidant enzymes *SOD1* (+33,2%), *SOD2* (+25,4%), and *CAT* (+58,4%) (Figure 4).

3.4. Confocal microscopy studies in human brains

Confocal microscopy was used to localize seipin and PEX16 expression in the hypothalami of healthy human brains and the PELD case. Image analysis revealed that seipin and PEX16 are expressed in neurons in the hypothalamic nuclei of both controls but not the PELD index case (Figure 5A-C). Interestingly, we only found cytoplasmic seipin in neurons (and not in astrocytes or oligodendrocytes). The main pattern observed in control brain regions was what we classified as the "granular profile," in which seipin is scattered throughout the neuronal cytoplasm and PEX16 appears to be closely intertwined in the free spaces (Figure 5A-B) very close to seipin, with a shape resembling vesicles (Figure 5D). We also observed intranuclear PEX16 and seipin in control hypothalamus images (Figure 5B). Finally, the seipin observed in neurons was localized in the cytoplasm in samples from the Celia's Encephalopathy case, and the staining was clearly diffused within the neuronal body and the proximal segment of the axons.. There was more seipin-containing nuclei in the Celia's Encephalopathy case compared to the control, while no PEX16 was found in the hypothalamus of this patient (Figure 5C).

4. Discussion

This study describes the differential expression of the *BSCL2* in the human brain and other tissues, and identifies *BSCL2-203* as the major transcript in the CNS. Remarkably, expression of this transcript appears to be reduced in the more primitive regions of the brain (diencephalon, mesencephalon and rombencephalon). *BSCL2-205/207/210* is primarily expressed in the extraneural tissues, and the transcript responsible for the Celia-seipin (*BSCL2-201*) is expressed very little but mainly in the caudate, one of the nuclei affected earliest in Celia's Encephalopathy (Araujo-Vilar et al., 2018). These

results indicate specific tissue functions for the different *BSCL2* transcripts, and these results coupled with the observation that the 64 amino acids corresponding to exon 1 and part of exon 2 of the *BSCL2*-203 transcript are identical or quasi-identical in hominidae primates (100-98%), very similar in other catharrine primates (95%), and similar in plathirrine primates (86-89%), while similarities are reduced in prosimians (75-55%) and in mice (52%) (Figure S2, Supplementary Material) suggest that the longer transcript should play some role in the encephalization process.

We have also found that the expression of seipin is noticeably reduced in the temporal lobe, amygdala and hypothalamus of the left hemisphere with age, all areas associated with memory and its consolidation, and the limbic system. Given that mitochondrial dysfunction is one of the hallmarks of aging (López-Otín et al., 2013), and that the proteomic results in preadipocytes of the Celia's Encephalopathy index case (Ruiz-Riquelme et al . 2015) indicated that mitochondrial superoxide dismutase (SOD2) and glutathione peroxidase were distinctively modulated, it is not surprising to find strong positive correlations between *BSCL2* and protective enzymes against oxidative stress such as *SOD1* and *SOD2*. The positive correlations between *BSCL2* and *PPARG*, *SOD1*, or *SOD2* could be explained by the important role played by *PPARG* in the activation of peroxisome proliferation, ultimately protecting against neurodegeneration by reducing the production of reactive oxygen species (Li et al., 2015; Qian et al., 2016; Zhou et al., 2016). Peroxisomal proliferation also reduces beta-amyloid induced toxicity in hippocampal neurons, reducing neuronal death and the loss of the neuritic network (Santos et al., 2005).

We investigated whether seipin is truly related to protective enzymes and peroxisomes in order to confirm our qPCR results in human brains. The significantly increased expression of the *SOD1*, *SOD2*, *CAT*, and *PPARG* genes corroborated the relationship between seipin and the protective proteins to oxidative stress in differentiated SH-SY5Y cells overexpressing *BSCL2*. Confocal microscopy in the hypothalami of healthy human brains also confirmed the close juxtaposition of seipin and *PEX16*, the latter appearing with a vesicle-like shape. This key protein for peroxisomal biogenesis is required for the de novo synthesis of peroxisomes (Kim et al., 2006) and is known to target to the ER before being trafficked to peroxisomes (Hua et al., 2015). Hofer et al. recently showed that *PEX16* is a *PPARG* target gene whose expression regulates peroxisome number and lipid metabolism, and demonstrated that it is also required for adipogenesis (Hofer et al., 2017). Studies in rodents have shown the beneficial effects of the pharmacological activation of peroxisome proliferation (with *PPARalpha* and *gamma* agonists) in Parkinson's disease and dyskinesia models (Barbiero et al., 2014; Grover et al., 2013).

The profiles observed in the confocal images suggest that seipin is involved in peroxisome biogenesis, probably at an early phase. The juxtaposition of seipin and *PEX16* observed in some neurons is consistent with the potential close proximity of peroxisomes and lipid droplet biogenesis areas (Binns et al., 2006), suggesting that peroxisomes and seipin are intimately associated. We can further speculate that peroxisomes with vesicle-like shapes may be pre-peroxisomal vesicles emerging from the ER. It should be noted that the structure of the lipid droplets and the peroxisomes are similar, both emerge from the ER, and there is a dialogue between both organelles (Shai et al., 2016). On the other hand, peroxisomes are very abundant in neurons and play a key role in protection against oxidative stress, and are also critical for the

synthesis of phospholipids. Finally, the peroxisome biomarker *PEX16* is barely detectable in the brain of the PELD case, where seipin is also scarce. Taken together, these data may suggest that seipin is playing a role in peroxisome biogenesis as a regulator of peroxisomal protein sorting during the first steps of biogenesis from the ER, similarly to what happens in the nascent lipid droplets (Shai et al., 2016), or could act as an essential factor in the recruitment of other peroxisomal membrane proteins to the ER together with *PEX16*, which subsequently transports them to the peroxisomes (Kim and Mullen, 2013). Correlation studies of gene expression, lentiviral overexpression experiments, as well as immunohistochemical and localization studies have allowed us to consolidate our hypotheses regarding the pathogenetic mechanisms of Celia's Encephalopathy (Ruiz-Riquelme et al . 2015). Seipin appears to have specific functions in the CNS, and could act as a neuroprotector, modulating the expression of *SOD* and *CAT* via *PPARG* by unknown mechanisms and promoting the proliferation of peroxisomes, thus decreasing free radicals and consequently protecting against neurodegeneration. The fact that seipin may be playing a role in peroxisome biogenesis makes them an interesting potential therapeutic target.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Acknowledgments

We are indebted to the parents of the patient for their collaboration in this study. We acknowledge confocal technical assistance by Mercedes Rivas Cascallar.

This work was supported by the Instituto de Salud Carlos III and the European Regional Development Fund, FEDER (grants number PI10/02873 and PI13/00314), by the

Consellería de Industria, Xunta de Galicia (grants number 10PXIB208013PR and ED341b 2017/19), and by Fundación Mutua Madrileña (Call 2015).

References

- Alaei, M. R., Talebi S, Ghofrani M, Taghizadeh M, Keramatipour M. 2016. Whole Exome Sequencing Reveals a BSCL2 Mutation Causing Progressive Encephalopathy with Lipodystrophy (PELD) in an Iranian Pediatric Patient. *Iran Biomed J.* 20, 295-301.
- Araujo-Vilar, D., Domingo-Jiménez R, Ruibal Á, Aguiar P, Ibáñez-Micó S, Garrido-Pumar M, Martínez-Olmos MÁ, López-Soler C, Guillín-Amarelle C, González-Rodríguez M, et al. 2018. Association of metreleptin treatment and dietary intervention with neurological outcomes in Celia's encephalopathy. *Eur J Hum Genet.* 26, 396-406. 10.1038/s41431-017-0052-8.
- Barbiero, J. K., Santiago RM, Persike DS, da Silva Fernandes MJ, Tonin FS, da Cunha C, Lucio Boschen S, Lima MM, Vital MA. 2014. Neuroprotective effects of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha and gamma agonists in model of parkinsonism induced by intranigral 1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine. *Behav Brain Res.* 274, 390-9. 10.1016/j.bbr.2014.08.014.
- Binns, D., Januszewski T, Chen Y, Hill J, Markin VS, Zhao Y, Gilpin C, Chapman KD, Anderson RG, Goodman JM. 2006. An intimate collaboration between peroxisomes and lipid bodies. *The Journal of Cell Biology.* 173, 719-731. 10.1083/jcb.200511125.
- Cartwright, B. R., Goodman, J. M. 2012. Seipin: from human disease to molecular mechanism. *J Lipid Res.* 53, 1042-55. 10.1194/jlr.R023754.
- Ebihara, C., Ebihara K, Aizawa-Abe M, Mashimo T, Tomita T, Zhao M, Gumbilai V, Kusakabe T, Yamamoto Y, Aotani D. 2015. Seipin is necessary for normal brain development and spermatogenesis in addition to adipogenesis. *Hum Mol Genet.* 24, 4238-49. 10.1093/hmg/ddv156.
- Grover, S., Kumar P, Singh K, Vikram V, Budhiraja RD. 2013. Possible beneficial effect of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPAR)--alpha and gamma agonist against a rat model of oral dyskinesia. *Pharmacol Biochem Behav.* 111, 17-23. 10.1016/j.pbb.2013.08.001.
- Guillen-Navarro, E., Sánchez-Iglesias S, Domingo-Jiménez R, Victoria B, Ruiz-Riquelme A, Rábano A, Loidi L, Beiras A, González-Méndez B, Ramos A et al. 2013. A new seipin-associated neurodegenerative syndrome. *J Med Genet.* 50, 401-9. 10.1136/jmedgenet-2013-101525.
- Hofer, D. C., Pessentheiner AR, Pelzmann HJ, Schlager S, Madreiter-Sokolowski CT, Kolb D, Eichmann TO, Rechberger G, Bilban M, Graier WF, et al. 2017. Critical role of the peroxisomal protein PEX16 in white adipocyte development and lipid homeostasis. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Molecular and Cell Biology of Lipids.* 1862, 358-368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbalip.2016.12.009>.
- Hua, R., Gidda SK, Aranovich A, Mullen RT, Kim PK. 2015. Multiple Domains in PEX16 Mediate Its Trafficking and Recruitment of Peroxisomal Proteins to the ER. *Traffic.* 16, 832-852. 10.1111/tra.12292.

- Ito, D., Suzuki, N. 2009. Seipinopathy: a novel endoplasmic reticulum stress-associated disease. *Brain*. 132, 8-15. 10.1093/brain/awn216.
- Kim, K. K., Adelstein RS, Kawamoto S. 2009. Identification of neuronal nuclei (NeuN) as Fox-3, a new member of the Fox-1 gene family of splicing factors. *J Biol Chem*. 284, 31052-61. 10.1074/jbc.M109.052969.
- Kim, K. K., Nam J, Mukoyama YS, Kawamoto S. 2013. Rbfox3-regulated alternative splicing of Numb promotes neuronal differentiation during development. *J Cell Biol*. 200, 443-58. 10.1083/jcb.201206146.
- Kim, P. K., Mullen, R. T., 2013. PEX16: a multifaceted regulator of peroxisome biogenesis. *Frontiers in Physiology*. 4, 241. 10.3389/fphys.2013.00241.
- Kim, P. K., Mullen RT, Schumann U, Lippincott-Schwartz J. 2006. The origin and maintenance of mammalian peroxisomes involves a de novo PEX16-dependent pathway from the ER. *The Journal of Cell Biology*. 173, 521-532. 10.1083/jcb.200601036.
- Li, G., Zhou L, Zhu Y, Wang C, Sha S, Xian X, Ji Y, Liu G, Chen L. 2015. Seipin knockout in mice impairs stem cell proliferation and progenitor cell differentiation in the adult hippocampal dentate gyrus via reduced levels of PPARgamma. *Dis Model Mech*. 8, 1615-24. 10.1242/dmm.021550.
- Livak, K. J., Schmittgen, T. D., 2001. Analysis of relative gene expression data using real-time quantitative PCR and the 2^{(-Delta Delta C(T))} Method. *Methods*. 25, 402-8. 10.1006/meth.2001.1262.
- López-Otín, C., Blasco MA, Partridge L, Serrano M, Kroemer G. 2013. The Hallmarks of Aging. *Cell*. 153, 1194-1217. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2013.05.039>.
- Magre, J., Delépine M, Khallouf E, Gedde-Dahl T Jr, Van Maldergem L, Sobel E, Papp J, Meier M, Mégarbané A, Bachy A, et al. 2001. Identification of the gene altered in Berardinelli-Seip congenital lipodystrophy on chromosome 11q13. *Nat Genet*. 28, 365-70. 10.1038/ng585.
- Qian, Y., Yin J, Hong J, Li G, Zhang B, Liu G, Wan Q, Chen L. 2016. Neuronal seipin knockout facilitates Abeta-induced neuroinflammation and neurotoxicity via reduction of PPARgamma in hippocampus of mouse. *J Neuroinflammation*. 13, 145. 10.1186/s12974-016-0598-3.
- Ruiz-Riquelme, A., Sánchez-Iglesias S, Rábano A, Guillén-Navarro E, Domingo-Jiménez R, Ramos A, Rosa I, Senra A, Nilsson P, García Á et al., 2015. Larger aggregates of mutant seipin in Celia's Encephalopathy, a new protein misfolding neurodegenerative disease. *Neurobiol Dis*. 83, 44-53. 10.1016/j.nbd.2015.08.006.
- Salo, V. T., Belevich I, Li S, Karhinen L, Vihinen H, Vigouroux C, Magré J, Thiele C, Hölttä-Vuori M, Jokitalo E, Ikonen E. 2016. Seipin regulates ER-lipid droplet contacts and cargo delivery. *EMBO J*. 35, 2699-2716. 10.15252/embj.201695170.
- Santos, M. J., Quintanilla RA, Toro A, Grandy R, Dinamarca MC, Godoy JA, Inestrosa NC. 2005. Peroxisomal Proliferation Protects from β -Amyloid Neurodegeneration. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 280, 41057-41068. 10.1074/jbc.M505160200.

- Shai, N., Schuldiner M, Zalckvar E. 2016. No peroxisome is an island - Peroxisome contact sites. *Biochim Biophys Acta*. 1863, 1061-9. 10.1016/j.bbamcr.2015.09.016.
- Sim, M. F., Talukder MM, Dennis RJ, O'Rahilly S, Edwardson JM, Rochford JJ. 2013. Analysis of naturally occurring mutations in the human lipodystrophy protein seipin reveals multiple potential pathogenic mechanisms. *Diabetologia*. 56, 2498-506. 10.1007/s00125-013-3029-3.
- Sim, M. F., Talukder MU, Dennis RJ, Edwardson JM, Rochford JJ. 2014. Analyzing the functions and structure of the human lipodystrophy protein seipin. *Methods Enzymol*. 537, 161-75. 10.1016/B978-0-12-411619-1.00009-4.
- Victoria, B., Cabezas-Agrícola JM, González-Méndez B, Lattanzi G, Del Coco R, Loidi L, Barreiro F, Calvo C, Lado-Abeal J, Araújo-Vilar D. 2010. Reduced adipogenic gene expression in fibroblasts from a patient with type 2 congenital generalized lipodystrophy. *Diabet Med*. 27, 1178-87. 10.1111/j.1464-5491.2010.03052.x.
- Wang, H., Becuwe M, Housden BE, Chitraju C, Porras AJ, Graham MM, Liu XN, Thiam AR, Savage DB, Agarwal AK, et al. 2016. Seipin is required for converting nascent to mature lipid droplets. *Elife*. 5. 10.7554/eLife.16582.
- Zhou, L., Chen T, Li G, Wu C, Wang C, Li L, Sha S, Chen L, Liu G, Chen L. 2016. Activation of PPARgamma Ameliorates Spatial Cognitive Deficits through Restoring Expression of AMPA Receptors in Seipin Knock-Out Mice. *J Neurosci*. 36, 1242-53. 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.3280-15.2016.

Figure legends

Figure 1: *BSCL2* transcripts expression

A) Summary of the relative expression of the three *BSCL2* transcripts across the primary brain divisions, the peripheral nervous system (PNS), and the extraneural tissues (ET). Details are available in Table S1 (Supplementary Material). B) Percent expression of *BSCL2* transcripts in CNS, PNS and ET. *BSCL2*-203 (blue), *BSCL2*-205/207/210 (red), and *BSCL2*-201 (green) expression are referred to as *BSCL2* total expression. C) Percentage expression of *BSCL2* transcripts in primary brain divisions: telencephalon (T), diencephalon (D), mesencephalon (M), metencephalon (Me), myelencephalon (My), spinal cord (SC); peripheral nervous system (PNS) and extraneural tissues (ET). All samples were analyzed in duplicate, n = 13. All results were normalized to the *18S* gene.

Figure 2: Correlations between *BSCL2* and age

Spearman correlation was calculated between *BSCL2*-203 relative expression and age. Significant correlations were observed for each zone: left temporal lobe, left amygdala and left hypothalamus, n = 13.

Figure 3: Morphological comparison between undifferentiated and differentiated SH-SY5Y

Morphological comparison between (A) undifferentiated and (B) differentiated SH-SY5Y cells over 7 days. Phase contrast light microscopy and GFP fluorescence images visualized under 10× magnification. Small red box indicates zoomed area (C), shown under 20× magnification.

Figure 4: Relative gene expression in SH-SY5Y differentiated cells overexpressing *BSCL2*-203 transcript.

Relative expression of: (A) *BSCL2*-203, (B) *PEX1*, (C) *PPARG*, (D) *SOD1*, (E) *SOD2*, and (F) *CAT*, *: p<0.05 vs cells transfected with empty vector. All samples were analyzed in duplicate, n = 4. Results were normalized to the *RNA polymerase II* gene.

Figure 5: Confocal microscopy images

Confocal microscopy images (under 63× magnification with 2x-zoomed images also included) showing immunofluorescence staining in the hypothalamus (HT) of (A) one male control case (59 years-old), (B) one female control case (75 years-old), and (C) an homozygous case c.985C>T, for PEX16 (green, Alexa 488), seipin (red, Alexa 555), and DAPI to label nuclei. Maximum image projection shows the granular profile (green arrow), intranuclear seipin (white arrow), and intranuclear PEX16 (yellow arrow), and merged images show no overlap between PEX16 and seipin (B). Analysis of the view from one section from the male control case indicates that PEX16 labeling was located as a peripheral ring, suggesting membrane labeling of vesicle-like PEX16 (D). Scale bar 25 and 50 μm.

Figure 1
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 2
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 3
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 4
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 5
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Supplementary Material

[Click here to download Supplementary Material: SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL.pdf](#)